
EFFECTS OF *LARONG PINOY* AS A PLAY-BASED LEARNING STRATEGY IN TEACHING ASIAN HISTORY

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ABSTRACT

In addressing multifaceted issues impacting academic engagement, learning, and overall performance, this action research aligns with the objectives of the "Traditional Games and Sports Act of 2010." This legislation aims to preserve Filipino identity and culture. This research enhances grade 7 students' mastery of Asian history by fostering interest, participation, a positive attitude, and developing essential values. Employing a Quasi-Experimental, non-equivalent group design, the researcher implemented the lesson "*Kontribusyon ng Timog at Kanlurang Asya at ang Pagkakakilanlan ng Kulturang Asyano*" during the third quarter, involving 69 grade 7 students from Regional Science High School III, A.Y. 2022-2023, divided into Controlled and Experimental Groups. Utilizing various descriptive analyses such as Shapiro-Wilk, Wilcoxon Signed Test, Kruskal-Wallis Test, and Pairwise Comparisons of Groups, the study revealed a significant improvement in post-test scores for both groups. Learners strongly agreed that the Play-Based Learning Strategy positively contributed to their academic development. This research established a noteworthy connection between learners' academic performance and perception of the employed strategy. Recommendations include expanding the sample size to 90% of the population and integrating the strategy more frequently for comprehensive data collection, emphasizing the importance of soliciting learner feedback on strategy implementation in the classroom.

Keywords: *Larong Pinoy*, Play-Based Learning Strategy, Asian History, Academic Performance

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INTRODUCTION

Secondary students frequently rank history as one of the most boring subjects, and teaching it in the modern classroom is challenging. The evolving nature of students in the

21st century, characterized by shorter attention spans (Hcsuper, 2017), adds complexity to making history engaging and impactful. Academic boredom, as Sharp et al. (2018) identified, poses a direct threat to learner engagement, learning outcomes, and overall academic performance.

Various teaching strategies have emerged in response to this challenge, among which Play-Based Learning stands out. This approach, rooted in learning through play (Daniels & Pyle, 2018), has garnered attention for its potential to make education more enjoyable and effective. Notably, research by Johnston and colleagues (2022) highlights the positive impact of a playful learning approach, emphasizing creativity, exploration, hands-on activities, and non-didactic methods in fostering student motivation and academic success.

This action research explores the potential of using "*Larong Pinoy*" as a Play-Based Learning Strategy in teaching Asian History to seventh-grade students. The choice of *Larong Pinoy* is grounded in its alignment with the "Traditional Games and Sports Act of 2010," introduced by former Senator Manny Villar to preserve Filipino identity and culture, particularly among the youth. Building on Avila's (2021) research, which underscores the benefits of traditional Filipino games in teaching and learning, this study seeks to enhance students' mastery of Asian History while promoting interest, participation, positive attitudes, and developing essential values. Ultimately, the researcher aims to identify the effects of *Larong Pinoy* as a Play-Based Learning Strategy in teaching Asian History, contributing valuable insights to the ongoing discourse on innovative and engaging teaching methodologies.

Statement of the Problem

This study determines the Effects of *Larong Pinoy* as a Play-Based Learning Strategy in Teaching Asian History to Grade 7 students of Regional Science High School III. Specifically, the study answers the following questions:

- 1) How may the respondents be described in terms of their pretest and post-test results?
- 2) How do the students perceive PBL (Play-Based Learning) in terms of:
 - a. Mastery of the Lesson;
 - b. Lesson Interest;
 - c. Class Participation; and
 - d. Attitude towards the subject?
- 3) Is there a significant effect on the learner's academic achievement from the post-test results after the implementation of *Larong Pinoy* and their perception of the use of the Play-Based Learning strategy?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher employed a quasi-experimental, non-equivalent group research design. The manipulation of the independent variable without randomly assigning participants to conditions is what Quasi-experimental research involves (Asio, 2021; Chiang et al., 2015). Specifically, a pretest-post-test non-equivalent groups design is administered, and both groups undertake the same pretest and post-test derived from the DepEd-prescribed learners' module during the specific parts of the lesson in the third quarter. The treatment group is given a pretest, then receives the intervention, and is given a post-test in the pretest-post-test non-equivalent groups design. In contrast, the control group is given a pretest, does not receive the intervention, and is given a post-test at the same time as the treatment group (Asio & Jimenez, 2020; Chiang et al., 2015).

Participants

The participants are the grade 7 students of the Regional Science High School III of the Academic Year 2022-2023 with their respective sections. There are two sections purposively chosen out of five sections. A total of 69 grade 7 students participated in the study. One of the two sections is a controlled group, while the other one is classified as the experimental group. The following classes are all under the heterogeneous classes. The researcher chooses the participants for the researcher is currently handling the grade 7 classes in the Regional Science High School III. The participants are anonymously described in the study.

Research Instrument

This study used the same pretest and post-test questions obtained from the DepEd-prescribed teaching module with the learning competencies the learners should manifest based on the *Araling Panlipunan* Curriculum Guide of the K-12 of DepEd. It was validated by one Master Teacher and one Head Teacher of *Araling Panlipunan*. For feedback on using the *Larong Pinoy* as a Play-Based Learning Strategy, the researcher used a validated perception survey based on the Likert Scale and the weighted mean validated by the Research Coordinator of Regional Science High School III.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The study used descriptive statistics and SPSS. Descriptive statistics is the initial stage of analysis used to describe and summarize data (Costa & Sarmento, 2019). The researcher tests the level of significance at 0.05.

The statistical treatments were employed to answer the specific questions raised in the study: Mean, Mean and Descriptive Interpretation, Shapiro-Wilk Test, and Wilcoxon Signed Test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section introduces the study's findings and the researcher's analysis and interpretation. They have included in this chapter the description of the participants based on their knowledge levels from their pretest and post-test results, the representation of the results of the perception of the participants from the experimental group with the usage of the intervention, the significant difference between the post-test results of the two groups, and the significant effect between the perception and the respondents' performance after using *Larong Pinoy* as a Play-Based Learning Strategy.

Respondents' Description Based on Their Pretest and Post-test Results

Pre- and post-tests are used to measure knowledge gained from participating in a training course (Shivaraju et al., 2017). To describe the participants from the two different groups (controlled and experimental), a descriptive analysis of the pretest and post-test using mean and standard deviation was utilized.

Table 2. Descriptive Analysis of Pretest and Post-test

Scores	Groups	N	Mean	SD
Pretest	Controlled	34	4.4412	1.23561
	Experimental	35	4.4286	1.00837
Post-test	Controlled	34	5.7941	1.53306
	Experimental	35	7.0000	0.80440

The analyzed data in Table 2 shows the description of the grade 7 respondents' performance at Regional Science High School III A.Y. 2022-2023 through the mean and standard deviation of the pretest and post-test scores of the respondents from both groups. The pretest scores of the Controlled Group attained a $M=4.4412$, $s=1.23561$, while the post-test scores attained $M=5.7941$, $s=1.53306$. Furthermore, the Experimental Group showcased a $M=4.4286$, $s=1.00837$ on their pretest scores and $M=7.0000$, $s=.80440$ on their post-test.

Table 3. Test of Normality

	Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.
Pretest Scores (<i>Controlled</i>)	.875	34	.001
Pretest Scores (<i>Experimental</i>)	.872	35	<.001
Post-test Scores (<i>Controlled</i>)	.947	34	.001
Post-test Scores (<i>Experimental</i>)	.823	35	<.001
Mastery of the Lesson	.859	35	<.001
Lesson Interest	.816	35	<.001
Class Participation	.803	35	<.001
Attitude Towards the Subject	.741	35	<.001

Table 3 presents the normality test of the pretest and post-test scores and the variables measuring the respondents' perceptions to provide a reliable statistical analysis and interpretation. The normality of the data was examined using the Shapiro-Wilk test for the pretest and post-test scores in both the controlled and experimental groups, as well as for the variables measuring mastery of the lesson, lesson interest, class participation, and attitude towards the subject.

The results indicated a significant departure from normality for all variables (pretest controlled: $p < .001$; pretest experimental: $p = .001$; post-test controlled: $p < .001$; post-test experimental: $p = .001$; mastery of the lesson: $p = .001$; lesson interest: $p = .001$; class participation: $p = .001$; attitude towards the subject: $p = .001$). These findings suggest that the assumption of normal distribution is violated for all examined variables. Consequently, non-parametric statistical tests are recommended for further analysis to account for the non-normal distribution of the data. Acknowledging and considering the implications of these departures from normality when interpreting the study results is essential.

Table 4. Wilcoxon Signed Test on Pretest and Post-test Scores

Scores	Z	Sig.	Remarks
Pretest and Post-test (Controlled)	-2.986	.003	Significant
Pretest and Post-test (Experimental)	-5.118	.001	Significant

This table analyzes the significant difference between the pretest and post-test scores using the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank test, which examined the differences between the pretest and post-test scores within the controlled and experimental groups across the given categories. The results revealed statistically significant differences in the pretest and post-test scores for the controlled group ($p = .003$) and the experimental group ($p < .001$). This result suggests significant improvements in the participants' scores from the pretest to the post-test in both groups. The findings indicate that the implemented intervention or treatment positively impacted the participants' performance, leading to a significant increase in their scores. These results highlight the effectiveness of the intervention in enhancing the learning outcomes for both the controlled and experimental groups within the specified categories. This finding is in line with the study of Nisa et al. (2018), which showcased that the increase in the scores of the students directly reflects the improvement of the learners.

Perception of the Respondents about PBL (Play-Based Learning)

Students' perceptions of class interaction and satisfaction may be the first step in exploring the role and weighting of different types of interaction with a view to student outcomes such as satisfaction and performance (Driver, 2002). Apart from the pretest and post-test results, teachers can also seek improvements in the learner's knowledge and overall development through collaborating with the learners in a specific strategy. Likert scale is applied as one of the most fundamental and frequently used psychometric tools

in educational and social sciences research (Joshi et al., 2015). Through this, a descriptive interpretation of the respondents' perception implied a particular impact on the teacher's teaching strategy.

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics on the Respondents' Perceptions of PBL (Play-Based Learning)

Parameters	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
Mastery of the Lesson	4.42	The learners strongly agree that the Play-Based Learning Strategy contributed to their development.
Lesson Interest	4.39	
Class Participation	4.45	
Attitude toward the subject	4.55	
Overall Mean	4.45	

Table 3 shows that the students have a strong agreement that the Play-Based Learning Strategy contributed to their development in the following parameters:

- a.) Mastery of the Lesson with the mean of 4.42,
- b.) Lesson Interest with 4.39,
- c.) Class Participation with 4.45, and
- d.) Attitude towards the subject attained a mean of 4.55.

The overall mean of 4.45 concludes that the students strongly agreed that the Play-Based Learning Strategy led them through the mastery of the lesson while being motivated, having an interest in the lesson, and participating during class while showing a positive attitude towards the subject of Asian history. These findings accord to Parker et al.'s study (2022), which showed that learning through play has emerged as an essential strategy to promote student engagement, inclusion, and holistic skills development.

Effect of Larong Pinoy and the Use of PBL on Learners' Academic Achievement

Table 6. Kruskal-Wallis Test on Post-test Scores and Students' Perception

	Kruskal-Wallis H	df	Sig	Remarks
Post-test Scores and Students' Perception	-5.118	4	.001	Significant

Table 6 examines the significant differences in the post-test scores and perception of the experimental group. The Kruskal-Wallis H test was utilized to examine the differences among the post-test scores, mastery of the lesson, lesson interest, class participation, and attitude towards the subject. The analysis yielded a significant result ($H = -5.118$, $df = 4$, $p < .001$), indicating significant differences among the variables. Further post hoc tests are recommended to determine the specific pairwise differences between the categories. These findings suggest variations in the participants' scores and perceptions across the measured aspects. The results emphasize the importance of considering

multiple factors, such as mastery of the lesson, lesson interest, class participation, and attitude towards the subject, when assessing the outcomes and experiences of the participants, in accord to, according to Machucho (2022) in his article about “Factors That Affect Students' Test Scores” there are also plenty of factors that have been seen for the students to do well in tests.

Table 7. Pairwise Comparisons of Group

Group Comparison	Sig.	Remarks
Post-test Scores and Mastery of the Lesson	<.001	Significant
Post-test Scores and Lesson Interest	<.001	Significant
Post-test Scores and Class Participation	<.001	Significant
Post-test Scores and Attitude Towards the Subject	<.001	Significant

In analyzing the data in Table 7, Pairwise comparisons were conducted to explore further the significant differences observed in the Kruskal-Wallis test among the post-test scores, mastery of the lesson, lesson interest, class participation, and attitude towards the subject. The results revealed significant associations between the post-test scores and mastery of the lesson ($p < .001$), lesson interest ($p < .001$), class participation ($p < .001$), and attitude towards the subject ($p < .001$). These findings indicate that there are distinct differences in the participants' post-test scores when comparing their levels of mastery of the lesson, interest in the lesson, class participation, and attitude toward the subject. The post hoc analyses provide valuable insights into the specific pairwise comparisons and highlight the importance of considering these factors when examining the outcomes and experiences of the participants in the study. In line with this is the study conducted by the group of Linda Price (2014) entitled "Modelling factors for predicting student learning outcomes in higher education," which resulted in the presentation of the heuristic model of student learning as a means to understanding the scope of factors to be considered in making predictions about student learning and the model has four main groups of factors: presage, perceptions, process, and product.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the researcher made the conclusions, which are as follows:

- 1) The grade 7 students of Regional Science High School III show a positive impact through the implementation of different learning strategies or interventions, with a significant increase in academic performance from their pretest and post-test scores in both groups.
- 2) Based on the perception of the learners, the Play-Based Learning strategy for teaching is effective in teaching Asian History for each parameter set, namely Mastery of the Lesson, Lesson Interest, Class Participation, and Attitude towards the subject received a descriptive interpretation of learners having a solid agreement that the

Play-Based Learning Strategy contributed to their development. So, it reflected the average weighted mean interpreted in the same analysis.

- 3) There is a significant effect between the learners' post-test scores in the Experimental Group and their perception of Play-Based Learning as a strategy for teaching Asian History. Each parameter significantly affects the learners' post-test scores, which the teachers should look out for when making predictions about the students' learning.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The researcher suggests the following in light of the findings:

- 1) It is recommended that the size of the sample population be improved for better generalization of the whole population. The next researcher may include at least 90% of the population to gather more data and perspective from the respondents.
- 2) When applying the Play-Based Learning strategy in teaching Asian History or any other subject, it is recommended to use it more often and apply better practice and instructions, providing low-cost materials and efficient time and space occupancy for better results and non-hazardous application of the said strategy.
- 3) The school coordinators may use the results of this study to seek the perceptions of the learners to improve the action plan and the school's resources, which will help them create a fun and innovative environment for the learners.
- 4) The Department of Education may use the data in this study to seek more competent and student-centered learning and teaching strategies, just like the Play-Based Learning Strategy that showcased a direct impact on the learners' academic performance.

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